

Fractional calculus as a generalized kinetic model for biochemical methane potential tests

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8 **Abstract**

9 This study presents a fractional calculus model as a generalized kinetic model for estimating the
10 maximum methane yield and degradation kinetics in biomethane potential (BMP) assays, a key
11 analytical method in anaerobic digestion research and application. The fractional model
12 outperformed common first-order kinetic models by yielding superior data fitting and properly
13 managing substrate heterogeneity. The fractional model showed robust performance in mono-
14 digestion, co-digestion and pre-treatment BMP assays with or without presence of large tailing
15 or sigmoidal patterns in the BMP curve. The main advantage of the fractional model over other
16 models is its ability to capture the complexities of the methane production process without
17 losing model accuracy. Assessment of the mathematical model revealed that for fractional
18 orders greater than 0.8 the Mittag-Leffler sequence could be transformed into a more
19 computationally efficient exponential function.

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20 1. Introduction

21 Anaerobic digestion (AD) plays a crucial role in wastewater treatment, particularly in
22 large-scale wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) because it facilitates the reduction of organic
23 matter and simultaneously generates renewable energy in the form of methane-rich biogas
24 (Appels et al., 2008; Calderon et al., 2021). AD technology enables WWTPs to be more energy
25 self-sufficient, even achieving energy self-sufficiency (Calderon et al., 2021; Gu et al., 2017;
26 Macintosh et al., 2019). However, AD technology has its limitations, including relatively slow
27 organic matter hydrolysis rates and susceptibility to inhibition by factors such as high ammonia
28 nitrogen or fatty acids (Elsamadony et al., 2021; Yenigün and Demirel, 2013; Angelidaki et al.,
29 2009). There is an interest in engineering AD plants to effectively operate on a large scale,
30 accommodating a wide range of substrates and process intensification techniques such as pre-
31 treatments and anaerobic co-digestion.

32 Engineering innovative approaches and implementing suitable pre-treatment methods
33 can lead to potential increases in hydrolysis rates, mitigate inhibitory effects, and enhance the
34 overall AD performance. However, before these advancements are implemented, they are first
35 scrutinized and researched at lab-scale. Biomethane potential assay (BMP) is the most widely
36 used lab-scale experimental platform in AD research and application for assessing substrate
37 quality and predicting methane production in full-scale AD plants as well as their performance
38 (Angelidaki et al., 2009; Hafner et al., 2020; Holliger et al., 2016). BMP assays have also been
39 used by researchers and practitioners to evaluate the feasibility and efficiency of intensification
40 techniques on methane generation and production rate prior to full-scale implementation
41 (Calderon et al., 2021; Park and Kim, 2015; Wang et al., 2013). BMP assays allow gaining insight
42 into the performance of AD under controlled conditions, leading to the systematic optimization
43 and identification of operational parameters.

44 Mathematical models have been widely utilized to assess improvements in methane
45 generation and evaluate the impact of various intensification techniques (Da Silva et al., 2022;
46 Pererva et al., 2020). Mathematical models facilitate the estimation of both maximum methane
47 production and degradation rate. However, existing empirical and semi-empirical models, such
48 as the two commonly used first-order approaches: (i) one-step one-fraction model that assumes
49 a single biodegradable fraction (namely 1k model), and (ii) one-step two fraction model (namely
50 2k model) that assumes two biodegradable fractions, each with distinct first-order degradation
51 rates, are not universally applicable (Da Silva et al., 2022). The 1k model often underestimates
52 the maximum methane production, while the 2k model can lead to overparameterization (Da

53 Silva et al., 2022). Despite the extensive research on the topic, the literature lacks a unified
54 alternative that accurately represents the complex biological interactions involved in methane
55 production. Many models have been used in the literature to describe methane generation in
56 BMP assays (Pererva et al., 2020; Strömberg et al., 2015; Donoso-Bravo et al., 2010). However,
57 most of these models do not offer parameters that are easily interpreted in the context of
58 anaerobic reactor design, e.g. Monod-type model, quadratic Monod-type model, and modified
59 Gompertz model. These models often lack a mathematical link to mass action laws, substrate
60 consumption kinetics, or phenomenological interpretation. These limitations make it
61 challenging to use model outputs in practical reactor design applications. The present research
62 focuses on the 1k and 2k models since these two models are based on first-order kinetics and
63 align closely with the ADM1. These models are phenomenological and simple, particularly useful
64 to model the degradation of particulate substrates, whose degradation is limited by hydrolysis.
65 The application of fractional calculus can offer a means to generalize the first-order model,
66 making it even more versatile and overcoming the limitations of 1k and 2k.

67 In wastewater treatment modelling and processing, idealized approximations are often
68 used to describe and design anaerobic digesters. These approximations assume factors such as
69 uniform mixing or utilizing simple kinetics models to describe the complex network of series-
70 parallel biological reactions involved in AD. However, to achieve a more realistic representation
71 of AD, novel mathematical approaches are necessary to accurately describe the intricate
72 biological network involved in methane production (Lopez-Vazquez et al., 2023; Magin, 2006;
73 Toledo-Hernandez et al., 2014).

74 Fractional calculus, an extension of traditional calculus, allows operations with non-
75 integer (i.e. fractional) orders of differentiation and integration. This mathematical tool is
76 gaining increasing interest across various engineering fields for describing complex phenomena.
77 Its flexibility and higher degree of freedom make it capable of modeling situations that
78 conventional methods may not accurately describe (Magin, 2006). Fractional calculus has been
79 successfully utilized to: (i) improve the mathematical description of batch fermentations and
80 thermal hydrolysis, surpassing typical mass balances (Toledo-Hernandez et al., 2014), (ii)
81 describe food processing drying operations and transport phenomena in biopolymers or
82 biological tissues, revealing that these media do not conform to Fickian diffusion behavior
83 (Simpson et al., 2013), (iii) improve the mathematical description of batch mineral flotation in
84 mining compared with other models commonly used in the mining field (Vinnett et al., 2015),
85 and (iv) describe the rheological characterization of thermal hydrolyzed waste activated sludge
86 with fractional derivatives in the Kelvin-Voigt model (Farno et al., 2018; Hii et al., 2019). These

87 examples show that fractional calculus serves as an innovative tool that enhances the
88 descriptive power of traditional models, surpassing the limitations of standard calculus in
89 accurately representing physical and chemical phenomena in a variety of fields of knowledge.

90 The objective of this study is to propose a generic mathematical model to estimate the
91 maximum methane production and degradation rate from BMP curves by incorporating
92 fractional calculus into kinetic modeling. The proposed fractional model will be compared with
93 the 1k and 2k models, widely used in the literature.

94 **2. Materials and methods**

95 **2.1. BMP assays**

96 BMP assays were conducted under mesophilic conditions following the procedures
97 outlined by Angelidaki et al. (2009) and Holliger et al. (2016). These tests were carried out by
98 triplicate using 160 mL serum bottles that were filled with inoculum (ca. 80 mL) and the amount
99 of substrate needed to achieve an inoculum-to-substrate ratio (ISR) of 2 on a volatile solids (VS)
100 basis. In each experiment, a blank test containing only inoculum was used to correct the
101 background methane production from the inoculum endogenous respiration. No external
102 buffers or trace elements were added. The inocula used in this research were collected from
103 well-functioning mesophilic anaerobic digesters operating at circumneutral pH values (7.3-7.8),
104 low volatile fatty acid concentration (< 200 mg/L), total ammoniacal nitrogen concentrations
105 below 1.5 gTAN/L and VS concentration values ranging between 15 and 30 g VS/L. The
106 headspace of each bottle was flushed with >99% N₂ gas to ensure anaerobic conditions.
107 Subsequently, the bottles were sealed with butyl rubber septa and aluminum crimp caps and
108 placed in a temperature-controlled incubator at mesophilic conditions (35-37 °C). Cumulative
109 methane production was monitored using the manometric method (Hafner and Astals, 2019).
110 In each sampling event, the headspace pressure was measured using a digital manometer and
111 the biogas composition analysed using a gas chromatograph as described elsewhere (Hafner et
112 al., 2020; Peces et al., 2020). Cumulative volumetric methane production is reported at standard
113 conditions (0 °C, 1 atm, dry).

114 The application of the fractional model and its comparison with the 1k and 2k models
115 were carried out using data from four distinct BMP studies. These include mono-digestion BMP
116 assays of cellulose (cellulose_1 and cellulose_2) from Hafner et al. (2020), and waste activated
117 sludge (WAS_1), primary sludge (PS) from Peces et al. (2020), and four slaughterhouse waste
118 streams (this study), including cattle paunch, cattle manure, DAF (dissolved air flotation) float

119 and tallow. The anaerobic co-digestion BMP results were obtained from Peces et al. (2020), who
120 co-digested oleic acid (OA) with waste activated sludge (WAS) and primary sludge (PS) at
121 different proportions. The selected BMP assays correspond to the co-digestion experiments that
122 increased the VS concentration by 50% and 100% (namely, WAS+50% OA, WAS+100% OA,
123 PS+50% OA, PS+100% OA). Ruiz-Hernando et al. (2014) results were used to evaluate substrate
124 pre-treatment, including untreated WAS (WAS_2), ultrasound pre-treated WAS at 27000
125 kJ/kgTS (US-WAS_2), alkaline pre-treated WAS treatment at 157 g NaOH/kg TS (NaOH-WAS_2),
126 and thermal pre-treated WAS at 80 °C for 15 minutes (T-WAS_2).

127 **2.2. Mathematical models for BMP assays**

128 **2.2.1. One biodegradable fraction first-order kinetic model (1k model)**

129 A single first-order kinetic model has frequently been used to describe the biochemical
130 conversion of an organic substrate to methane (Angelidaki et al., 2009; Donoso-Bravo et al.,
131 2010). For the BMP assay (batch reactor), substrate degradation is described by Equation 1.

132 Substrate (S)→Methane(B)

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -kS \quad (1)$$

133 where k is the first-order kinetic constant, S is the organic substrate concentration measured as
134 chemical oxygen demand (g COD/l), and t is time.

135 Solving the mass balance and applying stoichiometry, the first-order kinetic model can
136 be expressed as methane generated in time (Equation 2).

$$B(t) = B_0 (1 - e^{-kt}) \quad (2)$$

137 where B is the methane production (ml CH₄/g VS), B_0 is the maximum methane production (ml
138 CH₄/g VS), k is the first-order kinetic constant, and t is time. Hereafter, Equation (2) is referred
139 as 1k model.

140 **2.2.2. Two biodegradable fractions first-order kinetic model (2k model)**

141 Some authors have modified Equation 1 by dividing the substrate into two
142 representative biodegradable fractions with independent first-order rates, a rapid and a slowly
143 biodegradable fraction (Equation 3) (García-Gen et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2013).

$$B(t) = B_0 (f_{fraction}(1 - e^{-k_1t}) + (1 - f_{fraction})(1 - e^{-k_2t})). \quad (3)$$

144 Hereafter, Equation 3 is referred as 2k model. In this model, the substrate is
 145 characterized by two fractions and a distinct first-order kinetic constant for each fraction, that
 146 is k_1 and k_2 . In Equation 3, B is the methane production (ml/g VS), B_0 is the maximum methane
 147 production (ml/g VS), $f_{fraction}$ splits the substrate into rapidly and slowly biodegradable fractions,
 148 k_1 and k_2 are the first-order kinetic constants for each fraction, and t is the time.

149 2.2.3. Fractional model

150 A different methodology for characterizing substrate degradation in BMP assays is
 151 offered by the introduction of fractional kinetic differential equation (Equation 4) (Vinnett et al.,
 152 2015; Zhokh and Strizhak, 2018).

$$\frac{d^\alpha S}{dt^\alpha} = -k_\alpha \cdot S \quad (4)$$

153 In Equation 4, α represents the fractional order and k_α represents the anomalous kinetic
 154 parameter. The analytical solution of the general differential equation is the following
 155 (Baumann, 2021; Vinnett et al., 2015):

$$S(t) = S_0 \cdot E_\alpha(-k_\alpha \cdot t^\alpha) \quad (5)$$

156

$$E_\alpha(z) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^i}{\Gamma(\alpha \cdot i + 1)}; \quad (6)$$

157

158 where α represents the fractional order, Γ represents the "Gamma function", k_α represents the
 159 anomalous kinetic parameter and E_α is the Mittag-Leffler function. In the case where α is close
 160 to 1, the Mittag-Leffler function (Equation 6) becomes an exponential function, and the
 161 anomalous kinetic rate becomes a first-order model (Magin, 2006; Vinnett et al., 2015). This
 162 means that the fractional model includes the standard first-order model (Equation 1) as a
 163 specific solution. Thus, the fractional model is a more general model that can capture a broader
 164 range of dynamics depending on the α value. Equation 5 is the fractional model expressed for
 165 methane production in time.

$$B(t) = B_0 \cdot (1 - E_\alpha(-k_\alpha \cdot t^\alpha)); \quad (7)$$

166 where B is methane production (ml CH₄/g VS), B_0 is the maximum methane production (ml CH₄/g
167 VS), α is the fractional integration order, k_α is the anomalous kinetic constant, and t is time.

168 **2.2.4. Simplified fractional model**

169 The Mittag-Leffler (E_α) function can describe the exponential function as a series when
170 α is close to 1 (Podlubny, 1998; Magin, 2006). Thus, when α is close to 1, a possible simplification
171 of Equation 7 is to replace the exponential function with the Mittag-Leffler function (Equation
172 8). This approximation has been already used by Simpson et al. (2013, 2017) to model food
173 drying.

$$B(t) = B_0 \cdot (1 - e^{(-k_\alpha t^\alpha)}) \quad (8)$$

174

175 Equation 8 has already been used to model BMP curves (Pererva et al., 2020; Strömberg
176 et al., 2015). However, it was assumed to be an empirical model rather than a theoretical model.
177 This research shows that this empirical equation proposed by Pererva et al. (2020) and
178 Strömberg et al. (2015) has a fundamental explanation based on fractional calculus.

179 **2.3. Parameters estimation**

180 The model parameters were obtained using the least-squares method, *lsqcurvefit*
181 function, and 'trust-region-reflective' optimization algorithm in MATLAB (R2022b) using the
182 default tolerance (10^{-6}). This process aims to minimize the mean-squared discrepancies between
183 the collected experimental data and predictions from the model. The *nlparci* function was used
184 to calculate 95% confidence intervals. The Mittag-Leffler function was evaluated with an
185 accuracy of 10^{-14} .

186 The goodness-of-fit of the calibration was assessed using the coefficient of
187 determination (R^2) and the root mean square error (RMSE). These metrics provide an evaluation
188 of the accuracy of the model in predicting the experimental outcomes (Montgomery and
189 Runger, 2014; Motulsky and Ransnas, 1987).

190

191 3. Results and discussion

192 3.1. Mono-digestion BMP assays

193 Figure 1 presents the accumulated methane production over time of the mono-
194 digestion BMP assays. The three mathematical models were superimposed on these data,
195 except for the WAS_1, cattle paunch, and tallow. Table 1 shows the parameters of each model
196 derived from fitting the BMP curves and the associated 95% confidence intervals and the
197 goodness-of-fit parameters.

198 Celluloses, primary sludge, DAF float, and cattle manure BMP curves displayed a
199 characteristic first-order kinetics response. WAS_1 and cattle paunch showed a BMP curve with
200 significant tailing, i.e., a non-asymptotic deviation from the first-order exponential ideal trend
201 (Da Silva et al., 2022). Similarly, the 2k model presented large confidence intervals for the kinetic
202 parameters, except for BMP curves with large tailing like WAS_1 or cattle paunch. Despite these
203 variations, all three models showed compelling results, with high coefficients of determination
204 ($R^2 > 0.96$), reinforcing their significant reliability in predicting the overall behavior of the AD
205 process (except for the 2k model in tallow, which is unable to adjust the sigmoidal pattern).
206 However, confidence intervals encompassing zero can indicate overparameterization, which
207 could artificially inflate R^2 , implying that these values should be interpreted with caution
208 (Motulsky and Ransnas, 1987). The fractional model displayed a first-order fit in all model
209 adjustments ($\alpha=1$), except for the WAS_1 ($\alpha=0.75$) and cattle paunch ($\alpha=0.90$). In scenarios
210 where the α is close to 1, the 2k model provides hydrolysis constants similar to the 1k model,
211 with exception of tallow.

212

213 **Figure 1.** Cumulative methane production curves for mono-digestion of celluloses,
214 wastewater activated sludge (WAS_1), primary sludge (PS), cattle paunch, cattle manure,
215 DAF float and tallow. Experimental data (dots), 1k model (black line), 2k model (orange
216 line) and fractional model (blue line).

217

218 **Table 1.** Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for
219 the mono-digestion experiments.

220

221 3.2. Co-digestion BMP assays

222 Figure 2 shows the accumulated methane production over time of the co-digestion BMP
223 assays, where primary sludge and waste activated sludge were co-digested with oleic acid. Table
224 2 summarizes the least-squares adjusted model parameters, confidence intervals, and
225 goodness-of-fit parameters.

226 Figure 2 shows that the co-digestion BMP curves display a minor sigmoidal pattern,
227 potentially attributable to long-chain fatty acid inhibition since inhibition was more acute at
228 higher oleic acid loadings (Astals et al., 2021, 2014). This sigmoidal region was more pronounced
229 with higher co-digestion percentages of oleic acid in primary sludge. None of the co-digestion
230 BMP curves displayed tailing. Despite having the lowest RMSE, the confidence intervals for the
231 2k model parameters were larger than for the 1k model and fractional model. For all the co-
232 digestion BMP assays, the fractional model resembled a first-order fit. Like in Section 3.1, the 2k
233 model showed signs of overparameterization (as evidenced by a high confidence interval).

234

235 **Figure 2.** Cumulative methane production curves for co-digestion of waste activated sludge
236 (WAS_1) and primary sludge (PS) with oleic acid (OA). Experimental data (dots), 1k model (black
237 line), 2k model (orange line) and fractional model (blue line).

238

239 **Table 2.** Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for the
240 co-digestion experiments.

241

242 3.3. Pre-treatment BMP assays

243 Figure 3 shows the accumulated methane production over time for the untreated and
244 pre-treated WAS. WAS_2 was subjected to three distinct pre-treatments: alkaline, thermal and
245 ultrasound pre-treatment. Table 3 summarizes the least-squares adjusted model parameters,
246 confidence intervals, and goodness-of-fit parameters.

247 The BMP curves of all experiments showed evidence of tailing (Figure 3), more
248 pronounced in the untreated WAS. The first-order model was unable to reproduce the
249 asymptotic tendency of the BMP curves (Figure 3). Table 3 shows that when the fractional order
250 (α) deviates from 1, the confidence intervals for the 2k model become narrower. This is

251 especially noticeable for the untreated WAS₂. Conversely, as the α approaches 1, the 2k model
252 exhibits an increased uncertainty in methane generation.

253

254 **Figure 3.** Cumulative methane production curves for untreated and pre-treated WAS₂,
255 including alkaline, thermal and ultrasonication pre-treatment. Experimental data (dots), 1k
256 model (black line), 2k model (orange line) and fractional model (blue line).

257

258 **Table 3.** Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for pre-
259 treatment experiments.

260

261 **3.4. Simplified fractional model**

262 The simplified fractional model was used to model the untreated and pre-treated WAS
263 experiments (Section 3.1.3) because this dataset displayed the greatest variation in α among the
264 BMP assays under study (Table 3). The α varied from 0.66 for WAS₂ to 0.93 for NaOH-WAS₂.
265 The effects of simplification on the predictions can be observed in Figure 4 that compares the
266 variation in the α obtained with and without simplification of the fractional model. In
267 experiments where α was close to 1, the α derived from the simplified expression remained the
268 same. This is the case for the ultrasonicated pre-treated WAS. From a practical standpoint, there
269 was no statistical difference in the values in any of the cases. However, it is suggested that the
270 simplification be used when α is greater than 0.80 (Figure 4).

271

272 **Table 4.** Simplified fractional model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets),
273 R^2 and RMSE for the untreated and pre-treated WAS.

274

275 **Figure 4.** α obtained with the fractional model (Table 3) compared to the α obtained with
276 simplified fractional model (Table 4). The black solid line represents the bipartition of quadrant
277 ($y=x$).

278 3.5. Models fitting quality

279 All the R^2 are above 0.96 (except for the 2k model in tallow where the 2k model struggles
280 with the sigmoidal pattern), indicating that the three models (i.e., 1k, 2k and fractional model)
281 were able to approximate reasonably well the BMP curve under study (Montgomery and
282 Runger, 2014). It is important to note that high R^2 values indicate the model's ability to capture
283 the trend in the data but do not necessarily reflect the precision of the estimated parameters.
284 The most adequate models are those with the lowest RMSE, lowest variability in the confidence
285 intervals, and a smaller number of parameters (Motulsky and Ransnas, 1987). The fractional
286 model is the model that best fits these criteria and, therefore, it can be stated as a generalized
287 model.

288 The 1k model encounters fitting challenges, particularly when the BMP curve show
289 significant tailing, as clearly shown for WAS_1 and WAS_2 (Figures 1 and Figure 3, respectively).
290 The 2k model sometimes tends to overparameterize the dataset, which contributes to an
291 increase in the uncertainty of the model parameters. This is notably the case for substrates that
292 are well-fitted by the 1k model, such as PS (primary sludge) and cellulose (Table 1). In contrast,
293 the 2k model performs exceptionally well with substrates that display tailing, such as WAS. The
294 performance of the 2k model is robust and is comparable to the fractional model's effectiveness.
295 However, the fractional model can achieve a similar RMSE using one less parameter, regardless
296 of whether there is a large tailing, sigmoidal behavior, or a tendency towards the first model. In
297 that regard, the fractional model can capture single or multiple kinetics with fewer parameters,
298 and without risk of overfitting.

299 In the mono-digestion BMP assays (Table 1), the fractional model converged to the 1k
300 model ($\alpha=1$) for cellulose, primary sludge, cattle manure, DAF float and tallow; while the α was
301 lower for WAS_1 ($\alpha=0.75$), WAS_2 ($\alpha=0.75$), and cattle paunch ($\alpha=0.90$). In WAS_2, the 2k model
302 showed the best statistical indicators, though it was not far from the fractional model.

303 In the co-digestion experiments, the BMP curve was the best fitted by both the fractional
304 model and 1k model (Table 2), although the latter showed higher R^2 . The 2k model exhibited
305 larger confidence intervals than other model parameters. In this case, the fractional model
306 proved to be highly robust against the inhibition behavior that occurred at the beginning of the
307 BMP curves (sigmoidal behavior of the BMP curve).

308 In the pre-treatment BMP assays significant tailing was observed (Figure 3). Tailing was
309 particularly pronounced for WAS_2 and T-WAS_2. Thermal pre-treatment did not affect the

310 kinetic biodegradability of WAS_2, with the same behavior observed for both samples. As shown
311 by the higher methane yield, the alkaline and ultrasound pre-treatments were more disruptive
312 and managed to reduce the tailing effect of the BMP curve. In these cases, the pre-treatment
313 led to a more homogenized substrate from a kinetic point of view. As a result, the first-order
314 model improved the prediction of the generated methane and the α value of the fractional
315 model got closer to 1 (Table 3). As the pre-treatment was more aggressive, the α increased
316 because the substrate became more homogeneous, making the curve more closely aligned with
317 the first-order model. The 2k model fitted well the pre-treatment experiments, where large
318 tailings were evident (Figure 3). The R^2 and RMSE values were comparable to those obtained by
319 the fractional model, but the 2k model had one more parameter than the fractional model
320 (Table 3). In terms of the uncertainty of the methane yield, the 2k model exhibits more
321 uncertainty in more disruptive pre-treatments. Specifically, the 2k had an uncertainty of about
322 30% on the methane yield, while the fractional model showed less than 10% uncertainty in
323 methane yield.

324 When the α was not equal to one, the k_α parameter increased in comparison to the first-
325 order kinetic constant (Tables 1 and 3). This phenomenon may be linked to the heterogeneity of
326 reaction velocities in these substrates, suggesting that one portion of the substrate degrades
327 quickly while another portion degrades more slowly. This behavior was only observed in the
328 BMP curves that exhibited large tailing. Conversely, when the substrate is kinetically
329 homogeneous, the α is close to 1.

330 **3.6. Advantages and limitations of the fractional model**

331 The fractional model stands as a generalization of the 1k and 2k models, capable of
332 adjusting tailing trends of BMP curves with three parameters. The fractional model predicts the
333 maximum methane production where the 1k model tends to underestimate, limiting the
334 technical feasibility of estimating methane generation and offers stable fits where the 2k model
335 indicates overparameterization.

336 The use of fractional models is well justified for spatial derivatives (Podlubny, 1998;
337 Magin, 2010, 2006; Simpson et al., 2013; Zhokh and Strizhak, 2018). However, the introduction
338 of anomalous kinetics remains limited and its interpretation is still debatable. The natural way
339 to introduce and interpret the need for anomalous kinetics in AD is related to the non-
340 homogeneity of the substrate and the coexistence of different rates. To establish a general mass
341 balance for a discontinuous reactor, such as in the case of a BMP assay, the substrate
342 consumption term is integrated over the volume (Fogler, 2016):

$$\int -r_{substrate} \cdot dV = \frac{dS \cdot V}{dt} \quad (9)$$

343 Considering that the reaction rate is constant for each point in the control volume at the
344 same instant, the mass balance can be simplified to Equation 10.

$$-r_{substrate} = \frac{dS}{dt} \quad (10)$$

345 This simplified equation is equivalent to the mass balance defined in Equation 1.
346 However, in a complex matrix, such as in anaerobic digestion, assuming a constant reaction rate
347 throughout the volume is a strong assumption. As an alternative to using a system of partial
348 differential equations to account for the variation in the reaction rate with position in the
349 reactor, in this study it was assumed that the temporal variation is of a fractional type. This
350 approach transforms Equation 10 into a fractional derivative (anomalous rate) (Equation 11).

$$-r_{substrate,\alpha} = \frac{d^\alpha S}{dt^\alpha} \quad (11)$$

351 Equation 11 is a generalized version of the mass balance proposed in Equation 4. It is
352 important to note that in a heterogeneous reactor, where the reaction rate varies
353 simultaneously at different physical points, it is challenging to determine the spatial and
354 temporal dependence of the reaction rate at each point within the reactor. Confronted with this
355 challenge, the use of a fractional derivative allowed to maintain the structure of the mass
356 balance by incorporating an additional parameter (α). The fractional model eliminates the need
357 to solve a system of partial differential equations. Due to the variation of reaction rates over
358 time and position, determining the dependence of reaction velocity as a function of position in
359 a stirred tank becomes complex, especially when the system exhibits heterogeneous reaction
360 kinetics. As a result, Equation 9 is often solved under the assumption that, at a given time, the
361 reaction velocity remains constant for each infinitesimal volume element (Fogler, 2016). Under
362 this assumption, the reactor complexity is transformed into a fitting problem with an α
363 expression, which helps describe the complexity of the system. Thus, anomalous kinetics over
364 time stand as a promising alternative for modelling such complex systems.

365 As shown in the pre-treatment experiments, the BMP curves that resulted in a higher
366 maximum methane production were closer to the 1k model response. This means that the
367 heterogeneity of the reaction system decreased with the pre-treatment, thus eliminating the
368 need to vary the α from 1. By employing anomalous kinetics based on fractional calculation, the
369 complexity of identifying reaction rate variability across both time and space within each point
370 of the batch reactor is simplified. This approach addresses a challenge that, in principle, is not
371 feasible to handle experimentally.

372 The main limitation of the fractional model developed in this study is its inability to be
373 seamlessly integrated with the Anaerobic Digestion Model No. 1 (ADM1), the industry standard
374 for anaerobic digestion modelling (Zhang et al., 2015). This is primarily because of fundamental
375 differences in the conceptual design of the fractional derivative and the approach used in ADM1
376 (Batstone et al., 2002). However, despite this challenge, the fractional model has proven
377 valuable in accurately quantifying the maximum amount of methane that can be generated,
378 positioning it as a broadly applicable fundamental model. When the fractional order is equal to
379 1, the fractional model can be incorporated in the ADM1 because the kinetic parameter
380 corresponds to that of order one. Therefore, it can be used in the ADM1 to model the AD
381 process. However, considering the successful results of fractional equations in modeling
382 fermentations obtained by Toledo-Hernandez et al. (2014), it is conceivable that a redefined
383 ADM1 using fractional calculus could improve the AD predictions.

384 Another challenge associated with the implementation of the fractional model is the
385 need to program the Mittag-Leffler succession. Although this may pose an additional layer of
386 complexity, it is worth noting that this study provides the users with the necessary code to
387 replicate and implement the fractional model. Additionally, an easily implementable simplified
388 version of the model can be found in Equation 8 for α higher than 0.80.

389 **4. Conclusions**

390 The fractional calculus model overcomes the limitations of both 1k and 2k models. It accurately
391 predicts the maximum methane production where the 1k model tends to underestimate and
392 offers stable fits where the 2k model indicates overparameterization. The fractional model
393 efficacy and robustness was demonstrated in mono-digestion, co-digestion and pre-treatment
394 BMP assays, including BMP curves with or without the presence of large tailing or sigmoidal
395 pattern. The advantage relies on its ability to capture the methane production complexities
396 without losing model accuracy. Overall, these results showed that the fractional model is a
397 generalized model for BMP curves modelling.

398 **5. Supplementary material**

399 E-supplementary data of this work can be found in online version of the paper.

400 **6. Acknowledgements**

401 This work is supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities
402 (PID2019-111284RB-I00 and PID2020-116141GB-I00). Cristopher da Silva is grateful to the

403 Generalitat de Catalunya for his FI-SDUR grant (2020 FISDU 00554). Sergi Astals is grateful to the
404 Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities for his Ramon y Cajal fellowship (RYC-
405 2017-22372. Miriam Peces acknowledges the funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
406 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement
407 101023927. Finally, the authors would like to thank the Catalan Government for the quality
408 accreditation given to the Environmental Biotechnology research group (2017 SGR 1218) and
409 Laboratori de Càlcul Numèric (LaCàN) (2021 SGR 01049).

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Table 1. Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R² and RMSE for the mono-digestion experiments.

	Parameters	Cellulose_1	Cellulose_2	WAS_1	PS	Cattle Paunch	Cattle Manure	DAF Float	Tallow
1k model	B ₀ (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	352.9 (34.3)	340.3 (36.0)	252.9 (22.0)	436.1 (38.0)	358.6 (16.1)	180.4 (8.1)	833.4 (40.83)	822.8 (212.0)
	k (d ⁻¹)	0.36 (0.13)	0.27 (0.11)	0.23 (0.07)	0.28 (0.09)	0.08 (0.01)	0.08 (0.01)	0.04 (0.01)	0.09 (0.06)
	R ²	0.978	0.972	0.978	0.978	0.995	0.997	0.997	0.960
	RMSE	20.29	22.39	12.45	23.21	9.83	3.60	18.67	67.83
2k model	B ₀ (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	464.9 (9.7·10 ⁵)	427.8 (9.3·10 ⁹)	280.6 (12.4)	432.5 (1.1·10 ⁶)	375.0 (12.1)	180.3 (17.5)	814.0 (69.2)	568.1 (485.6)
	f _{fraction} (-)	0.75 (1.54·10 ³)	0.80 (1.73·10 ⁷)	0.50 (0.10)	0.85 (772.40)	0.63 (0.26)	0.52 (6.68·10 ⁶)	0.12 (1.13·10 ⁷)	0.68 (5.02·10 ⁷)
	k ₁ (d ⁻¹)	0.37 (0.01)	0.27 (0.01)	0.53 (0.14)	0.28 (0.27)	0.13 (0.04)	0.09 (0.004·10 ⁶)	0.04 (0.01·10 ⁷)	0.16 (0.01·10 ⁷)
	k ₂ (d ⁻¹)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.01)	0.08 (0.03)	0.29 (2.96)	0.03 (0.02)	0.09 (0.05·10 ⁶)	0.04 (0.01·10 ⁷)	0.16 (0.01·10 ⁷)
	R ²	0.978	0.972	0.999	0.978	0.999	0.997	0.996	0.827
	RMSE	20.27	22.39	1.86	21.18	3.17	3.61	20.76	131.62
Fractional model	B ₀ (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	352.0 (41.0)	340.4 (48.6)	294.8 (20.3)	437.3 (37.4)	375.7 (14.4)	180.5 (12.8)	828.4 (29.3)	823.50 (205.0)
	α (-)	1.00 (0.15)	1.00 (0.24)	0.75 (0.08)	1.00 (0.05)	0.90 (0.06)	1.00 (0.09)	1.00 (0.01)	1.00 (0.01)
	k _α (d ^{-α})	0.36 (0.15)	0.27 (15)	0.28 (0.03)	0.28 (0.10)	0.10 (0.01)	0.08 (0.02)	0.04 (0.01)	0.09 (0.04)
	R ²	0.978	0.972	0.999	0.979	0.999	0.997	0.998	0.960
	RMSE	18.16	20.20	2.86	20.95	4.72	3.62	17.74	64.97

Table 2. Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for the co-digestion experiments.

	Parameters	WAS_1 + 50% OA	WAS_1 + 100% OA	PS+ 50% OA	PS+ 100% OA
1k model	B_0 (ml CH_4/g VS)	487.9 (29.5)	617.75 (61.9)	637.0 (73.5)	760.8 (127.1)
	k (d^{-1})	0.26 (0.06)	0.21 (0.07)	0.20 (0.08)	0.16 (0.07)
	R^2	0.989	0.978	0.974	0.961
	RMSE	17.65	33.23	39.01	57.87
2k model	B_0 (ml CH_4/g VS)	475.6 (58.5)	617.4 (96.9)	622.7 (111.4)	761.8 (229.1)
	$f_{fraction}$ (-)	0.62 ($7.78 \cdot 10^5$)	0.99 ($1.3 \cdot 10^7$)	0.95 ($1.32 \cdot 10^7$)	0.99 ($1.3 \cdot 10^7$)
	k_1 (d^{-1})	0.28 ($2.89 \cdot 10^5$)	0.21 ($1.01 \cdot 10^3$)	0.21 ($1.52 \cdot 10^3$)	0.16 ($2.63 \cdot 10^3$)
	k_2 (d^{-1})	0.28 ($4.78 \cdot 10^3$)	0.21 ($1.15 \cdot 10^6$)	0.21 ($2.92 \cdot 10^4$)	0.16 ($2.63 \cdot 10^5$)
	R^2	0.987	0.978	0.967	0.961
	RMSE	17.70	33.23	39.96	57.87
Fractional model	B_0 (ml CH_4/g VS)	488.6 (25.5)	622.55 (62.2)	638.1 (105.1)	752.6 (182.4)
	α (-)	1.00 (0.01)	1.00 (0.05)	1.00 (0.15)	1.00 (0.28)
	k_α ($d^{-\alpha}$)	0.26 (0.02)	0.21 (0.07)	0.21 (0.05)	0.16 (0.06)
	R^2	0.990	0.977	0.970	0.960
	RMSE	15.74	30.36	35.72	53.17

Table 3. Model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for untreated and pre-treated WAS₂, including alkaline (NaOH-WAS₂), thermal (T-WAS₂) and ultrasonication (US-WAS₂) pre-treatment.

	Parameters	WAS ₂	NaOH-WAS ₂	T-WAS ₂	US-WAS ₂
1k model	B_0 (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	128.2 (10.1)	176.8 (6.3)	134.4 (7.0)	145.7 (6.6)
	k (d ⁻¹)	0.29 (0.09)	0.32 (0.04)	0.30 (0.06)	0.31 (0.05)
	R^2	0.961	0.992	0.983	0.987
	RMSE	7.79	4.99	5.50	5.16
2k model	B_0 (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	144.3 (5.2)	193.2 (75.6)	158.4 (19.8)	169.0 (50.9)
	f_{fraction} (-)	0.47 (0.05)	0.79 (0.15)	0.64 (0.04)	0.69 (0.10)
	k_1 (d ⁻¹)	0.78 (0.14)	0.39 (0.15)	0.46 (0.06)	0.42 (0.10)
	k_2 (d ⁻¹)	0.08 (0.02)	0.05 (0.22)	0.04 (0.04)	0.04 (0.09)
	R^2	0.999	0.997	0.999	0.998
	RMSE	0.89	3.27	0.81	1.84
Fractional model	B_0 (ml CH ₄ /g VS)	160.5 (13.5)	181.6 (11.0)	147.6 (11.3)	154.9 (11.3)
	α (-)	0.66 (0.07)	0.93 (0.12)	0.81 (0.11)	0.87 (0.12)
	k_α (d ^{-α)}	0.32 (0.03)	0.33 (0.05)	0.33 (0.04)	0.33 (0.05)
	R^2	0.999	0.994	0.996	0.994
	RMSE	1.48	4.37	2.75	3.46

Table 4. Simplified fractional model parameters and their 95% confidence interval (in brackets), R^2 and RMSE for the untreated and pre-treated WAS.

	Parameters	WAS_2	NaOH-WAS_2	T-WAS_2	US-WAS_2
Simplified fractional model	B_0 (ml CH_4 /g VS)	145.0 (9.80)	178.2 (7.3)	140.6 (7.9)	149.5 (7.6)
	α (-)	0.59 (0.08)	0.93 (0.19)	0.75 (0.14)	0.82 (0.17)
	k_α (d $^{-\alpha}$)	0.39 (0.03)	0.34 (0.08)	0.37 (0.07)	0.33 (0.08)
	R^2	0.998	0.993	0.994	0.992
	RMSE	1.85	4.77	3.34	4.04

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Figure 1. Cumulative methane production curves for mono-digestion for celluloses, wastewater activated sludge (WAS), primary sludge (PS), cattle paunch, cattle manure, DAF float and tallow. Experimental data (dots), 1k model (black line), 2k model (orange line) and fractional model (blue line).

Figure 2. Cumulative methane production curves for co-digestion of wastewater activated sludge (WAS_1) and primary sludge (PS) with oleic acid (OA). Experimental data (dots), 1k model (black line), 2k model (orange line) and fractional model (blue line).

Figure 3. Cumulative methane production curves for untreated and pre-treated WAS₂, including alkaline (NaOH-WAS₂), thermal (T-WAS₂) and ultrasonication (US-WAS₂) pre-treatment. Experimental data (dots), 1k model (black line), 2k model (orange line) and fractional model (blue line).

Figure 4. Fractional order obtained with the fractional model (Table 3) compared to the fractional order obtained with simplified fractional model (Table 4). The black solid line represents the bipartition of quadrant ($y=x$).

Authors contribution statement

Cristopher Da Silva: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing - original draft, Visualization, Software. **Miriam Peces:** Investigation, Data curation, Writing - review and editing, Visualization. **Aldonza Jaques:** Formal analysis, Writing - review and editing. **Jose Muñoz:** Conceptualization, Writing -review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Joan Dosta:** Writing - review and editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Sergi Astals:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review and editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

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